

ConsenCUS

CO2 pull market analysis

ConsenCUS deliverable 8.2 Version 27.04.2022

Date	Version	Status	Initials	Changes Marked
27.04.2022	1	First version	KH	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and Innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101022484.

Version Control Sheet

WP	WP8 - CO2 clusters & value chain design
Lead Author:	Kate Harboe
Contributing Author(s):	Lukas Kung with further support from ConsenCUS partners
Reviewed by:	Evrin Ursavas
Due Date:	01.05.2022
Date:	27.04.2022
Version:	1
Contact:	kha@dgc.dk ; e.ursavas@rug.nl
Dissemination Level:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU: Public <input type="checkbox"/> CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

Date: pick a date
Document number: Type document number
Version: Type version number

Table of contents

Table of contents	3
1 Introduction.....	4
1.1 Background	4
1.2 Methodology.....	4
2 Pull market	6
2.1 Potential CO ₂ storage sites	6
2.2 Potential CO ₂ end users – renewable energy projects	11
3 Conclusions.....	14

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

The main objective of work package "CO₂ clusters & value chain design" is the temporal and spatially optimal design and planning of CCUS clusters and networks.

In this respect the following objectives are identified:

- Two European CO₂ clusters (South-East/North-West) will be defined and analyzed for optimal value chain design.
- A value chain optimization framework will be developed to analyze how location, size and timing of investments are affected by alternative technologies and infrastructures using mixed integer linear programming models.
- Minimal cost for net-zero CO₂ configurations will be determined with detailed analysis of the novel technologies developed in WP2 and WP3 as components of the optimization framework.

This specific deliverable corresponds to the second task, which is the analysis of the push market for CO₂. Here the main aim is to outline CO₂ storage sites and CO₂ utilization sites in two regions: Northwest Europe (NL, UK and Denmark) and Southeast Europe (Greece, Bulgaria and Romania). These will be used as input for the cluster framework model to analyze different configurations and assess the potential of these industries to contribute to a CO₂ cluster.

1.2 Methodology

As an outcome of this task, a database has been prepared for use in cluster configurations. The sources of information for the CO₂ storage sites are from European CO₂ storage database ("CO₂Stop") and company websites. The source for information of the CO₂ utilization sites are company websites on green hydrogen projects. It is expected that hydrogen produced from renewable energy is used in combination with CO₂ to form hydrocarbons, for example methanol, urea, or aviation fuel.

Main specifications of the database are as follows:

- The list covers six countries: Bulgaria, Denmark, Netherlands, Romania, United Kingdom and Greece
- For each CO₂ storage site the following information has been identified:
 - Geographical location.
 - Expected minimum, mean, and maximum reservoir capacity.
 - Expected minimum and maximum storage injection rate if announced. If not announced, the site is only an indication of potential CO₂ storage.
 - Expected year of operation if announced.
- For each potential CO₂ utilization site based on expected nearby hydrogen production, the following information has been identified:
 - Geographical location.
 - Expected capacity of electrolysis.
 - Expected year of operation.

It is important to highlight that the database is not fully comprehensive because it is based on public available information and the list can change rapidly as some projects may be matured or cancelled and new projects are announced.

2 Pull market

2.1 Potential CO₂ storage sites

Project	Company	Country	Area	Onshore/ Offshore	Type	Lat	Long	Expected reservoir capacity_mi n [Mill ton CO2]	Expected reservoir capacity_mea n [Mill ton CO2]	Expected reservoir capacity_ma x [Mill ton CO2]	Expected storage injection capacity_mi n [Mill ton CO2/year]	Expected storage injection capacity_ma x [Mill ton CO2/year]	Expected year of operatio n	Report ing year
GreenSand (phase1)	INEOS, Maersk Drilling and Wintershall Dea	Denmark	Danish North Sea	Offshore		56.94307133	4.833694679			2000	0.5	1	2025	2021
GreenSand (phase 2)	INEOS, Maersk Drilling and Wintershall Dea	Denmark	Danish North Sea	Offshore		56.94307133	4.833694679			2000	4	8	2030	2021
Northern Light (phase 1)	Equinor, Shell and TotalEnergies	Denmark	Northern Lights Carbon Capture Plant Site, Western Norway	Offshore		60.55466498	4.886592083				0.8	1.5	2024	2021
Northern Light (phase 2)	Equinor, Shell and TotalEnergies	Denmark	Northern Lights Carbon Capture Plant Site, Western Norway	Offshore		60.55466498	4.886592083				3.5	5		2021
Bifrost	TotalEnergies, DUC, DTU, Ørsted	Denmark	Danish North Sea	Offshore		56.55714618	4.338945533					3	2027	2021
		Denmark	Gassym (Gassum formation)	Onshore		56.58095	9.997302		586					2021
		Denmark	Havnsø (Gassum formation)	Onshore		55.752912	1.132373		306					2020
		Denmark	Hanstholm (Gassum formation)	Offshore		57.115181	8.617232		1333					2020
		Denmark	Rødby (Bunter formation)	Onshore		54.692884	11.389895		341					2020
		Denmark	Thisted	Onshore		56.962573	8.703749		2418					2020
		Denmark	Voldum	Onshore		56.367152	10.172827		854					2020
		Denmark	Tønder	Onshore		54.934638	8.869144		229					2020
		Denmark	Vedsted	Onshore		55.295734	8.669158		39					2020
		Denmark	Thorning	Onshore		56.301301	9.300788		296					2020
		Denmark	Røsnæs	Onshore		55.756293	10.872523		429					2020
		Denmark	Hanstholm (Skagerak formation)	Offshore		57.115181	8.617232		3441					2020

Project	Company	Country	Area	Onshore/ Offshore	Type	Lat	Long	Expected reservoir capacity_mi n [Mill ton CO2]	Expected reservoir capacity_mea n [Mill ton CO2]	Expected reservoir capacity_ma x [Mill ton CO2]	Expected storage injection capacity_mi n [Mill ton CO2/year]	Expected storage injection capacity_ma x [Mill ton CO2/year]	Expected year of operatio n	Report ing year		
Porthos	Energean Plc	Denmark	Skagerak	Offshore		57.885657	9.846543				1000					
		Denmark	Legin	Onshore		56.974176	8.475263			1619				2020		
		Denmark	Skive	Onshore		56.578397	8.987516			334				2020		
		Denmark	Helgenæs	Onshore		56.144784	10.522853			307				2020		
		Denmark	Stenlille	Onshore		55.541259	11.591094				51					
		Greece	Prinos-Kavala basin	Offshore		40.859525	24.460384				30				2021	
		Greece	Mesohellenic Trough Eptachori	onshore		40.253329	21.18611			1277					2020	
		Greece	Mesohellenic Trough Pentalofo	onshore		40.202477	21.119673			166					2020	
		Greece	Evros - Northern Greece (studied)	onshore	Deposit of zeolite	41.676699	26.116487			24,5					2018	
		Greece	Vourinos - Western Macedonia (studied)	onshore	Magnesium silicates site	40.173061	21.664625			70	500				2018	
		Greece	Epanomi Gas Fields - Thessaloniki	onshore	Depleted gas field	40.425557	22.918768			2					2020	
		Greece	Thessaloniki basin	Offshore	Saline aquifers	40.425557	22.918768			640					2020	
		Acorn	Dutch government in partnership with Air Liquide, Air Products, ExxonMobil and Shell.	Netherlands	North Sea	Offshore	Depleted oil and gas field	52.394039	3.591177				37	2.5	2030	2021
Netherlands	Dutch North Sea Field K 14/15 #6			Offshore	Depleted oil and gas field					165		3			2012	
Netherlands	Dutch North Sea Field K04/05 #7			Offshore	Depleted oil and gas field	53.16401	3.37874				140		3		2012	
Netherlands	Dutch North Sea Field K07/08/10 #8			Offshore	Depleted oil and gas field	53.05444	2.64442				195		3	6	2012	
Netherlands	Dutch North Sea Field L10/K12 (#9)			Offshore	Depleted oil and gas field	53.39971	3.45250				175		6		2012	
Netherlands	Q1 - Lower Cretaceous (#1)			Offshore	Saline aquifer	53.23892	4.48522	110		225				10	2012	
Netherlands	P, Q - Lower Cretaceous (#2)			Offshore	Saline aquifer	52.87908	4.32620				360			10	2012	
Netherlands	F15, F18 – Triassic (#3)			Offshore	Saline aquifer	52.33534	3.86420				650		1	3	2012	
Netherlands	L10, L13 – Upper Rotliegend (#4)			Offshore	Saline aquifer	54.08517	4.37847				60			5	2012	
Netherlands	Step graben – Triassic (#5)			Offshore	Saline aquifer	53.39971	3.45250				190		1	3	2012	
Acorn	UK and Scottish Government in partnership with Storegga, Shell and Harbour Energy	United Kingdom	North East of Scotland	Offshore	Sandstone rock	55.02173	4.63050					5	10	2030	2021	
		United Kingdom	Hamilton gas field, East Irish Sea	Offshore	Depleted oil and gas field	58.07788	1.39833							5	2016	
		United Kingdom	Bunter Sandstone Formation	Offshore	SA w/ HC	53.55975	-	3.44333								2012
		United Kingdom	Leman Sandstone	Offshore	SA w/ HC	54.01256145	1.270766915	2467	13294	41716					2012	
				Offshore		53.41040451	1.662881162							2012		

Project	Company	Country	Area	Onshore/ Offshore	Type	Lat	Long	Expected reservoir capacity_mi n [Mill ton CO2]	Expected reservoir capacity_mea n [Mill ton CO2]	Expected reservoir capacity_ma x [Mill ton CO2]	Expected storage injection capacity_mi n [Mill ton CO2/year]	Expected storage injection capacity_ma x [Mill ton CO2/year]	Expected year of operatio n	Report ing year
		United Kingdom	Frigg Sandstone Member	Offshore	SA w/o HC	60.26116714	1.787321754	190		370	584			2012
		United Kingdom	Heimdal Sandstone Unit	Offshore	SA w/o HC	59.74385267	1.390364695	955	12220		35322			2012
		United Kingdom	Tay Sandstone Member	Offshore	SA w/o HC	57.23100394	0.931104947	2		339	1954			2012
		United Kingdom	Forties Sandstone Member	Offshore	SA w/ HC	57.40650591	1.333267513	1814	26132		94496			2012
		United Kingdom	Cromarty Sandstone member	Offshore	SA w/o HC	57.65876976	0.483668425	130		372	739			2012
		United Kingdom	Mousa Formation	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.50572631	0.131068766	7015	14614		24691			2012
		United Kingdom	Flugga Sandstone Unit	Offshore	SA w/ HC	58.88268307	1.241967256	90		427	1098			2012
		United Kingdom	Hermod Sandstone Unit	Offshore	SA w/o HC	59.86254865	2.004044033	6		25	43			2012
		United Kingdom	Skadan Sandstone Unit	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.84081403	1.428697578	16		66	106			2012
		United Kingdom	Teal Sandstone Member	Offshore	SA w/o HC	59.98602134	1.861474749	64		221	533			2012
		United Kingdom	Skroo Sandstone Unit 1	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.44589262	1.326676878							2012
		United Kingdom	Skroo Sandstone Unit 2	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.75346301	1.364000909							2012
		United Kingdom	Skroo Sandstone Unit 3	Offshore	SA w/o HC	59.03577081	1.489534256	0		6	22			2012
		United Kingdom	Ormskirk Sandstone Unit 1	Offshore	SA w/ HC	53.84996758	-3.591165477	317	1775		5201			2012
		United Kingdom	Ormskirk Sandstone Unit 3	Offshore	SA w/o HC	54.61266974	-4.015058916	160		339	756			2012
		United Kingdom	Ormskirk Sandstone Unit 2	Offshore	SA w/o HC	53.97813933	-4.322672571							2012
		United Kingdom	Maureen Sandstone Unit	Offshore	SA w/ HC	58.21578772	0.79972593	576	4753		23814			2012
		United Kingdom	Balder Sandstone Unit	Offshore	SA w/ HC	58.25739145	1.297052341	12		30	198			2012
		United Kingdom	Collyhurst Sandstone Unit 1	Offshore	SA w/o HC	53.64289086	-3.495554679	176		2141	6381			2012
		United Kingdom	Collyhurst Sandstone Unit 2	Offshore	SA w/o HC	54.18760934	-4.003390749	287		1221	1837			2012
		United Kingdom	Collyhurst Sandstone Unit 3	Offshore	SA w/o HC	53.860338	-3.752542046	0		1	5			2012
		United Kingdom	Otter Sandstone Formation	Offshore	SA w/ HC	50.48017971	-2.123035721	124		1266	3988			2012
		United Kingdom	St Bees Sandstone Unit	Offshore	SA w/o HC	54.0491228	-3.782995749	1251	11099		39210			2012
		United Kingdom	Plattendolomit Unit	Offshore	SA w/ HC	53.82348909	1.120746834	1822		5467	10691			2012
		United Kingdom	Bridport Sands Unit	Offshore	SA w/o HC	50.43990744	-2.362225847	66		394	1206			2012
		United Kingdom	Argyll Carbonate Member	Offshore	SA w/ HC	55.6156112	2.589332214	2		102	672			2013
		United Kingdom	Bruce Sandstone Unit 2	Offshore	SA w/o HC	59.54083545	1.441588352	4		27	66			2013
		United Kingdom	Bruce Sandstone Unit 3	Offshore	SA w/o HC	59.76576174	1.649075527	2		18	42			2013
		United Kingdom	Coracle Sandstone Member	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.2773093	-2.092944992							2013
		United Kingdom	Punt Sandstone Member	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.17110999	-2.212539743							2013
		United Kingdom	Nansen Unit 1	Offshore	SA w/o HC	59.57500391	1.683197404	20		103	251			2013
		United Kingdom	Nansen Unit 2	Offshore	SA w/o HC	61.025333	1.383647487	118		592	1448			2013
		United Kingdom	Zechsteinkalk Unit	Offshore	SA w/ HC	52.90913317	1.711234761	77		435	662			2013
		United Kingdom	Mains Formation Unit	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.02051505	-2.884392644							2013
		United Kingdom	Ling Sandstone Unit	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.71720275	1.369190691							2013
		United Kingdom	Innes Carbonate Unit 1	Offshore	SA w/ HC	56.99690664	1.327078416							2013
		United Kingdom	Innes Carbonate Unit 2	Offshore	SA w/ HC	59.46595965	1.447913884							2013
		United Kingdom	Innes Carbonate Unit 3	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.23877318	-2.19303777							2013
		United Kingdom	Innes Carbonate Unit 4	Offshore	SA w/o HC	56.6739964	-1.616389278							2013
		United Kingdom	Hugin Unit 1	Offshore	SA w/ HC	58.5903549	1.468365662							2013
		United Kingdom	Hugin Unit 2	Offshore	SA w/o HC	59.57468641	1.721857234							2013
		United Kingdom	Hugin Unit 3	Offshore	SA w/o HC	61.0451345	-0.042674323							2013
		United Kingdom	Hopeman Sandstone Unit	Offshore	SA w/ HC	58.20706413	-2.662753417							2013
		United Kingdom	Fulmar Sandstone Unit	Offshore	SA w/ HC	56.95215835	1.584457018	4284	13693		28350			2013

Project	Company	Country	Area	Onshore/ Offshore	Type	Lat	Long	Expected reservoir capacity_mi n [Mill ton CO2]	Expected reservoir capacity_mea n [Mill ton CO2]	Expected reservoir capacity_ma x [Mill ton CO2]	Expected storage injection capacity_mi n [Mill ton CO2/year]	Expected storage injection capacity_ma x [Mill ton CO2/year]	Expected year of operatio n	Report ing year
		United Kingdom	Brae Formation Unit 2	Offshore	SA w/ HC	58.3736002	1.257632749	1		9	20			2013
		United Kingdom	Brae Formation Unit 3	Offshore	SA w/ HC	58.4818942	1.292376104	40		18	35			2013
		United Kingdom	Firth Coal Unit 2	Offshore	SA w/o HC	57.68459839	0.283912465							2013
		United Kingdom	Firth Coal Unit 3	Offshore	SA w/o HC	56.72668762	-1.611665486	3		12	94			2013
		United Kingdom	Schooner Unit 2	Offshore	SA w/o HC	53.836905	1.102120261							2013
		United Kingdom	Schooner Unit 3	Offshore	SA w/o HC	54.96733753	-1.260147436							2013
		United Kingdom	Schooner Unit 4	Offshore	SA w/o HC	54.38312054	-0.11186769							2013
		United Kingdom	Skagerrak Unit 2	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.90608955	0.017911116	120		604	1466			2013
		United Kingdom	Skagerrak Unit 3	Offshore	SA w/o HC	57.71737356	-0.189419286	16		79	192			2013
		United Kingdom	Skagerrak Unit 4	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.50505217	-0.26613468	46		233	566			2013
		United Kingdom	Skagerrak Unit 5	Offshore	SA w/o HC	56.75116938	1.032836761	55		278	673			2013
		United Kingdom	Skagerrak Unit 6	Offshore	SA w/o HC	57.11599325	0.464188844	41		206	500			2013
		United Kingdom	Spilsby Sandstone Unit 4	Offshore	SA w/o HC	52.52674382	1.950839233							2013
		United Kingdom	Stroma Member 2	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.5892017	-0.109884202	2		28	68			2013
		United Kingdom	Spilsby Sandstone Unit 1	Offshore	SA w/o HC	53.21527171	1.009234572							2012
		United Kingdom	Spilsby Sandstone Unit 2	Offshore	SA w/o HC	52.98999584	2.972573917							2012
		United Kingdom	Spilsby Sandstone Unit 3	Offshore	SA w/o HC	52.50611505	2.841529026							2012
		United Kingdom	Hewett Sandstone	Offshore	SA w/ HC	52.75632078	2.098283704	73		431	1407			2012
		United Kingdom	Westcoe Coal Unit	Offshore	SA w/ HC	53.41221623	1.949274719	11		193	1680			2012
		United Kingdom	Millstone Grit Unit	Offshore	SA w/ HC	53.91525737	1.284855686							2012
		United Kingdom	Schooner Unit 1	Offshore	SA w/ HC	54.02117382	2.289560211							2012
		United Kingdom	Mey Sandstone Unit	Offshore	SA w/ HC	57.90681172	0.51003188	3602		21852	57369			2012
		United Kingdom	Dornoch Formation	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.78460513	0.117670578	2381		8037	20373			2012
		United Kingdom	Grid Sandstone Member	Offshore	SA w/o HC	59.26360079	1.256975533	185		1389	10866			2012
		United Kingdom	Cormorant Formation	Offshore	SA w/o HC	60.80170167	1.349299848	4405		16361	35891			2012
		United Kingdom	Magnus Sandstone	Offshore	SA w/ HC	61.65806246	1.369053232							2013
		United Kingdom	Alness Spiculite Member	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.19647106	-2.24029356	67		209	395			2013
		United Kingdom	Auk Formation Unit	Offshore	SA w/ HC	57.43753649	1.449261167	718		8845	23695			2013
		United Kingdom	Beatrice Formation Unit	Offshore	SA w/ HC	58.13984112	-2.678307758	262		736	1447			2013
		United Kingdom	Birch Sandstone Member	Offshore	SA w/ HC	58.57685531	1.31487553	6		16	24			2013
		United Kingdom	Brae Formation Unit 1	Offshore	SA w/ HC	58.73056136	1.40228476	33		132	516			2013
		United Kingdom	Brent Group	Offshore	SA w/ HC	61.11118902	1.351743902	945		2184	4722			2013
		United Kingdom	Britannia Sandstone Formation	Offshore	SA w/ HC	57.98727746	0.958721089	31		193	441			2013
		United Kingdom	Brora Coal Formation	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.04728613	-3.173829178	9		77	451			2013
		United Kingdom	Bruce Sandstone Unit 1	Offshore	SA w/ HC	59.40809981	1.622366693	1		5	11			2013
		United Kingdom	Buchan Formation Unit	Offshore	SA w/ HC	57.62933247	0.991259851	9		105	15435			2013
		United Kingdom	Burns Sandstone Member	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.2444636	-1.713678204	175		1110	549			2013
		United Kingdom	Claymore Sandstone Member	Offshore	SA w/ HC	58.37975515	0.05752686	76		508	1181			2013
		United Kingdom	Emerald Formation	Offshore	SA w/ HC	60.63316206	1.046046327	11		22	38			2013
		United Kingdom	Findhorn Formation	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.32562213	-1.924522418	569		4742	13909			2013
		United Kingdom	Firth Coal Unit 1	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.46002239	0.191587784							2013
		United Kingdom	Orcadia Formation Unit	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.54806338	-1.116824114	12		228	4018			2013
		United Kingdom	Orrin Formation	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.11730823	-3.06978955	28		88	200			2013
		United Kingdom	Piper Formation	Offshore	SA w/ HC	58.52308737	-0.099266889	625		2139	5156			2013

Project	Company	Country	Area	Onshore/ Offshore	Type	Lat	Long	Expected reservoir capacity_mi n [Mill ton CO2]	Expected reservoir capacity_mea n [Mill ton CO2]	Expected reservoir capacity_ma x [Mill ton CO2]	Expected storage injection capacity_mi n [Mill ton CO2/year]	Expected storage injection capacity_ma x [Mill ton CO2/year]	Expected year of operatio n	Report ing year
		United Kingdom	Skagerrak Unit 1	Offshore	SA w/ HC	57.34975	1.622155763	1045	5266	12779				2013
		United Kingdom	Strath Rory Formation	Offshore	SA w/o HC	58.1750398	-1.689008596	3	56	1536				2013
		United Kingdom	Stroma Member 1	Offshore	SA w/o HC	57.91356717	-0.270813703	5	61	151				2013
		United Kingdom	Statfjord Unit 1	Offshore	SA w/ HC	59.57640308	1.691074468	168	390	914				2013
		United Kingdom	Statfjord Unit 2	Offshore	SA w/ HC	60.87245822	1.700831353	104	254	738				2013
		United Kingdom	Captain Sandstone Member	Offshore	SA w/ HC	58.31935923	-1.778747197	291	806	1710				2013
		Bulgaria	Pavlikeni zone	Onshore	SA w/o HC	43.24403	25.77506	400	460	550				2014
		Bulgaria	Pleven zone	Onshore	SA w/ HC	43.46492	24.94056	1600	1800	2000				2014
		Bulgaria	Marash	Onshore	SA w/o HC	43.19772	26.92565	15	17.5	25				2014
		Bulgaria	Totleben	Onshore	SA w/o HC	43.46492	24.94056	4	5.3	8				2014
		Bulgaria	Popovo zone	Onshore	SA w/o HC	43.3476	26.2264	18	21.6	25				2014
		Bulgaria	Yambol-south	Onshore	SA w/o HC	42.3541	26.5671	22	27	65				2014
		Bulgaria	Cherkovo	Onshore	SA w/o HC	42.476	26.9902	19	24	86				2014
		Bulgaria	Galata	Onshore	SA w/ HC	43.0458	28.1978	0	0	0				2014
		Bulgaria	Dolna Kamchia	Onshore	SA w/ HC	42.98744	27.84644	45	56.16	65				2014
		Bulgaria	Galabovo	Onshore	SA w/o HC	42.241	25.6906	80	85	105				2014
		Bulgaria	Maritsa	Onshore	SA w/o HC	42.2362	24.9271	70	72	90				2014
		Romania	Meotian Formation from Getic Depression SU	Onshore	SA w/ HC	44.87263479	24.04848311	335	400	1343				2014
		Romania	Meotian Formation from Mio-Pliocene Subzone in Muntenia SU	Onshore	SA w/ HC	45.03638914	26.05275693	994.3	1000	2485.6				2014
		Romania	Middle Devonian Formation from Moesian Platform SU	Onshore	SA w/ HC	44.567963	25.57064	1674.8	1800	6699.4				2014
		Romania	Middle Jurassic Formation from Moesian Platform SU	Onshore	SA w/ HC	44.4504134	25.38886967	1325	1500	2208				2014
		Romania	Miocene from Pannonian Depression SU	Onshore	SA w/ HC	46.5285927	21.76499826	2194.4	2400	4388.8				2014
		Romania	Pliocene Formation from Pannonian Depression SU	Onshore	SA w/ HC	46.40186444	21.55043564	676.4	800	2705.6				2014
		Romania	Pontian Formation from Moesian Platform SU	Onshore	SA w/ HC	44.52785048	25.33697915	1355.7	1500	12906.3				2014
		Romania	Sarmatian Formation from Moesian Platform SU	Onshore	SA w/ HC	0	0	912.4	1000	1459.8				2014
		Romania	Sarmatian Formation from North-Dobroudjan Promontory SU	Onshore	SA w/ HC	45.89314946	27.64581375	6319.8	800	1239.6				2014
		Romania	Sarmatian Formation from Getic Depression SU	Onshore	SA w/ HC	44.73331554	23.67256645	810.2	1000	3240.6				2014
		Romania	Sarmatian Formation from Transylvanian Depression SU	Onshore	SA w/ HC	46.3955961	24.58135046	2696.8	3000	5393.5				2014
		Romania	Upper Burdigalian from Mio-Pliocene Subzone in Muntenia SU	Onshore	SA w/ HC	45.028576	25.960891	234.4	300	937.7				2014
		Romania	Silurian Formation from Moldavian Platform SU	Onshore	SA w/o HC	47.18069735	27.24906213	1234.9	1400	4939.8				2014
		Romania	Sarmatian Formation from Moldavian Platform SU	Onshore	SA w/ HC	46.99168013	26.82930242	603.2	700	2412.8				2014
		Romania	Tescani Beds	Onshore	SA w/ HC	47.071928	26.331536	242.3	400	969.3				2014

SA w/ HC: Saline Aquifer with hydrocarbon fields
SA w/o HC: Saline Aquifer without hydrocarbon fields

2.2 Potential CO₂ end users – renewable energy projects

Project	Company	Country	City	Lat	Long	Expected end product	Expected capacity of electrolysis [MW]	Expected year of operation	Reference	Year of reference
Green Fuels for Denmark	Ørsted, Copenhagen Airports, A. P. Møller-Maersk, DSV, DFDS, SAS, Everfuel, NEL, Molslinjen, Haldor Topsøe, COWI, Københavns Kommune, Region Hovedstaden	Denmark	Copenhagen	55.6748	12.63969	Sustainable aviation fuel	1300	2030	https://orsted.com/en/media/newsroom/news/2020/05/485023045545315	2021
Green Hydrogen Hub	Green Hydrogen Hub Denmark	Denmark	Viborg	56.4481	9.389887	Hydrogen	1000	2030	https://greenhydrogenhub.dk/about/	2021
GreenLab Skive	GreenLab, Everfuel, Eurowind Energy, Green Hydrogen Systems, Norlys Holding, RE:Integrate, Energinet, Danish Gas Technology Center, E.on Danmark, DTU Energy, EA Energy Analyses	Denmark	Skive	56.646	8.974627	Methanol	100	2026	https://www.greenlab.dk/knowledge/from-good-intentions-to-great-reductions/	2021
HySynergy	Crossbridge Energy, Everfuel, Aktive Energi Anlæg, Trefor Elnet, Energinet, TVIS, EWII	Denmark	Fredericia	55.569	9.748656	Hydrogen	1000	2030	https://www.everfuel.com/projects-archive/hysynergy/	2021
HyBalance	Air Liquide, Hydrogenics, Ludwig-Bölkow-Systemtechnik, Centrica and Hydrogen Valley.	Denmark	Hobro	56.6262	9.824565	Hydrogen	1200	2030		
Nordjyllandsværket	Copenhagen Infrastructure Partners, RenoNord, Aalborg Forsyning	Denmark	Aalborg	57.0725	10.04216	Methanol	300-400	2028	https://aalborgforsyning.dk/privat/nyheder-og-presse/seneste-nyheder/6-december-2021-power-to-x-anlaeg-i-aalborg-skal-indfange-co2-og-bruge-det-til-gront-braendstof/	2021
e-Fuels Vordingborg	Arcadia eFuels	Denmark	Vordingborg	54.9949	11.87599	eKerosene and eNaphta	-	2024	https://www.arcadiaefuels.com/arcadia-efuels-announces-its-first-efuels-plant-location-in-vordingborg-denmark	2022
Hydrogen Delta	Institute for Sustainable Process Technology (ISPT), Nouryon, Shell, Yara, OCI Nitrogen, Gasunie, DOW Chemical, Ørsted, Frames, ECN part of TNO, Utrecht University and Imperial College London	Netherlands	North Sea Port	multiple locations		Hydrogen	1000	2030	https://www.smartdeltaresources.com/en/hydrogen-delta	2021
Djewels	Nouryon, BioMCN, DeNora, Gasunie, Hinicio, and McPhy	Netherlands	Delfzijl	53.3342	6.919937	Methanol	20		https://djewels.eu/	2021
H2.50	BP, Port of Rotterdam, Nouryon	Netherlands	Rotterdam	51.9278	4.476586	Hydrogen	250	2025	https://www.portofrotterdam.com/en/news-and-press-releases/hydrogen-plants-provide-new-source-renewable-heat-south-holland	2021

Project	Company	Country	City	Lat	Long	Expected end product	Expected capacity of electrolysis [MW]	Expected year of operation	Reference	Year of reference
Westereems	RWE, Innogy	Netherlands	Eemshaven	53.4549	6.830406	Hydrogen	100		https://www.rwe.com/-/media/RWE/documents/07-presse/rwe-generation-se/2019-06-18-rwe-and-innogy-investigate-production-of-green-hydrogen-in-the-netherlands.pdf	2021
Hemweg hub Amsterdam	Vattenfall, Metropool Regio Amsterdam, Port of Amsterdam	Netherlands	Amsterdam Metropool Region			Hydrogen	100		https://www.topsectorenergie.nl/sites/default/files/uploads/TKI%20Gas/publicaties/Overview%20Hydrogen%20projects%20in%20the%20Netherlands%20versie%201mei2020.pdf	2020
H2ermes	Port of Amsterdam, TATA steel, Nouryin	Netherlands	Amsterdam	52.379	4.915007	Sustainable fuels	100		https://www.topsectorenergie.nl/sites/default/files/uploads/TKI%20Gas/publicaties/Overview%20Hydrogen%20projects%20in%20the%20Netherlands%20versie%201mei2020.pdf	2020
North2 (phase 1)	Gasunie, Groningen Seaports, Shell Nederland, Equinor and RWE	Netherlands	Eemshaven	53.4549	6.830406	Hydrogen	4000	2030	https://www.north2.eu/en/	2021
North2 (phase 2)	Gasunie, Groningen Seaports, Shell Nederland, Equinor and RWE	Netherlands	Eemshaven	53.4549	6.830406	Hydrogen	10000	2040	https://www.north2.eu/en/	2021
HyNetherlands	Gasunie, Engie	Netherlands	Eemshaven	53.4549	6.830406	Hydrogen	100	2025	https://tractebel-engie.com/en/news/2021/hynetherlands-one-of-europe-s-largest-green-hydrogen-plants-to-accelerate-the-journey-to-carbon-neutrality	2021
HYFIVE	GREATER LONDON AUTHORITY	United Kingdom	LONDON	51.5056	-0.08001	hydrogen for transport	?			
Shoreham port	Getech, h2green	United Kingdom	Brighton			hydrogen for transport	5		https://www.h2green.co.uk/news/agreement-to-develop-clean-energy-hub-for-shoreham-port-sussex/	2021
Inverness	Getech, h2green, SGN	United Kingdom	Inverness			hydrogen for transport and heating	?		https://www.h2green.co.uk/news/sgn-and-h2-green-launch-inverness-hydrogen-hub-plan-to-cut-transport-emissions/	2021
Gigastack	ITM Power Trading Ltd	United Kingdom	at Philips 66 Humber Refinery	53.6317	-0.244064	hydrogen	100	2025	https://gigastack.co.uk/	
Dolphyn	Environmental Resources Management Limited (ERM)	United Kingdom	North sea			hydrogen	2 (2020), 100-300 (2030), 1000 (2035)		https://ermdolphyn.erm.com/p/1	2022
HyGreen	BP	United Kingdom	Teesside area			hydrogen	500	2030	https://www.bp.com/en/global/corporate/what-we-do/gas-and-low-carbon-energy/h2teesside.html	2021

Project	Company	Country	City	Lat	Long	Expected end product	Expected capacity of electrolysis [MW]	Expected year of operation	Reference	Year of reference
Port of Cromarty Firth	ScottishPower, Pale Blue Dot (A Storegga Group Company), Port of Cromarty Firth, Glenmorangie, Whyte & Mackay and Diageo.	United Kingdom	Port of Cromarty Firth	57.6861	- 4.173391	hydrogen	35	2024	https://pocf.co.uk/hydrogen/	2021
WHITELEE SOLAR / HYDROGEN / BESS	ScottishPower, BOC and ITM Power	United Kingdom	Whitelee	55.6956	- 4.339347	hydrogen	20	2023	https://www.scottishpowerrenewables.com/pages/whitelee_solar_hydrogen_bess.aspx	2021
H100 Fife	SGN, Cadent, Northern Gas Network, Wales&West Utilities, ofgem, Scottish government	United Kingdom	Levenmouth			hydrogen	5	2023	https://h100fife.co.uk/about-h100/	
Port of Immingham	Associated British Ports (ABP), Siemens Energy UK (SEU), Toyota Tsusho UK (TTUK), Uniper Technologies UK (UTL), Uniper Hydrogen UK (UHU)	United Kingdom	Humber cluster			hydrogen	20	2025	https://www.toyota-tsusho.com/english/press/detail/211005_004900.html#:~:text=Under%20the%20Project%20plan%2C%20feasibility,Port%20of%20Immingham%20by%202025.	2021
	Trafford Green Hydrogen	United Kingdom	Manchester	53.4342	- 2.412358	hydrogen	10 (2023), 200		https://www.edie.net/news/8/Plans-filed-for-green-hydrogen-production-hub-near-Manchester/42567/	2021
Surf'n'turf		United Kingdom	Orkney: Eday & Mainland			hydrogen	0.5		https://www.surfnturf.org.uk/	
		United Kingdom	Orkney			hydrogen	?		https://www.edie.net/news/10/Green-hydrogen-facility-planned-for-oil-terminal-in-Orkney-Total-Energies-Scotland-/	2021

3 Conclusions

This task has contributed to the identification of potential large CO₂ users in two regions in South-East and North-West Europe. Emitters identified in deliverable 8.1 together with the potential end users and storage sites identified here will provide the necessary input for assessing the cluster configurations.